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MODELS OF TRANSLATION PROCESS AND THEIR TEACHING TO STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the article the author attempts to prove that it is possible to study innovative pedagogical technologies and translation process models in accordance with modern requirements.

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At present, innovative pedagogical technologies are being developed in accordance with modern requirements. In recent years, many definitions of translation emerged as a process. All of them are of approximate nature, since it is impossible to know what is happening in the human mind at the present stage of scientific advancement when it is translated from one language into another.

Translation, which is the product of brain activity, will one day be discovered scientifically, and its laws will be discovered through the efforts of experts in various fields. Specialists in the field of higher physiology of nerve activity, biochemistry, psychophysiology, physics and other sciences are working to unravel this mystery. Models of translation process are built on the observations, logical conclusions of translators, etc., according to linguists. When it is possible to examine these theoretical laws on the basis of logical facts, some of the conclusions are false and

false. It would be a mistake to conclude that one should refrain from modeling the translation process. They probably indicate a need for a closer look at creating such schemes and descriptions. The

most common translation processes today are: situational, semantic, transformative, semantic-semiotic, conformity, communicative-functional, informative, equivalence theory, and more. Let us examine some of them.

The situational (denotative) model is the unchanging basis of the original language and translation units, the consistency of these units with subjects, events, and information. In linguistics, they are called denotations or referents. Denotates are essentially the same for all humanity. Any text that reflects a certain subject matter, conclusion, or eventual event is formed by adapting it with different denotations. From this it is understood that translation is a process of replacing denotate material symbols, which is, that words in one language are interchangeable with other language symbols and the corresponding denotations. In other words, the interpreter accepts events and ideas in one material form and expresses them in another, while denotations do not change. At times, however, there may be no denotations in the community that serve the language of translation. At this time the translator uses different translation compensation methods to store the translation text and accurately describe the event. Interpretation of the denotative translation process is widespread despite the presence of opposites and its limited interpretability.

The semantic model of the translation process is constructed through the continuous existence of inter-language coherence and the structural analysis of language units. In the translation process, elements that give elemental content and their components are selected from the original text and selected units that are similar or similar to their content. In this way, the translator analyzes the components of the text and synthesizes the content in the translation language. The usual content of any speech unit is content, stylistic, style, etc is considered as a set of characteristics. Corresponding words are chosen accordingly. In this interpretation, the translation process takes place not only at the level of words and sentences, but also at the level of simple components of the content. The greater the degree of compatibility of such simple elements in the original and the language of the translation, the more logical the translation becomes. The semantic model is related to the presence of deep content categories in the language and structures that are specific to all languages. The translation process begins with a comparison of these deep contents. Of course, there are many critics of this model. The transformational model was formed under the influence of the ideas of transformative grammar. In the construction of such a model, the translator is defined as the translation of the language of the translator into the language of the translation. The translator accepts the original text and produces a cross-language translation of the mind and presents it as a ready translation.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹

A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.²

¹ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

² Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

The article considers the role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan. In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, sustainable development of tourism occurs as a result of economic integration and the systematic improvement of international relations. With the innovative development of the economy, the role and prestige of tourism in the national economy is growing. Tourism is one of the most profitable sectors of the economy.³

Today richness of Uzbek terminology is mainly due to the use of other languages and word formation is giving. The main factor that determines the stability of a particular terminological system in a particular field is its regularity.⁴

The communicative method as the ultimate goal of learning involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, speech, subject, socio-cultural, educational and compensatory competencies.⁵

The main purpose of teaching computer graphics in school in the article is to teach students the order and rules of computer-aided drawing of graphic information, such as drawings, diagrams and schemes, performed in the disciplines of drawing and engineering graphics.⁶

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁷

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.⁸

Synonyms are formed from the combination of the Greek words syn" together"+ onoma" name", which is an important means of increasing the effectiveness of speech, a clearer, more vivid, logical and diverse expression of thought.⁹

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.¹⁰

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis,

³ Abdullaevna, A. A., & Kizi, K. D. R. (2020). Role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism. *European science*, (1 (50)).

⁴ Bakhtiyorovna, N. M., & Zoirovna, N. I. Terms and Terminology in the Uzbek and English Languages. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 173-176.

⁵ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁶ Ruzimurodova, Z., & Mamatov, D. K. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 4(11), 136-140.

⁷ Pulatova, S. (2021). SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM "THE BOOK BAG". *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ*.

⁸ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

⁹ Mirxanova, G. R. (2021). EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(2), 96-105.

¹⁰ Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.

at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.¹¹

In the national economy, as in the economic systems of a number of foreign countries, the concept of public-private partnership (PPP) is being actively implemented.¹²

This article discusses the socio-philosophical importance of gender equality in today's increasingly globalized world. At the same time, in Uzbekistan, which is developing rapidly in all directions, the current issues of women's legal freedoms, protection of their legitimate interests, social relations of women in society and the development of society, social cohesion, family, traditions, It has been scientifically stated that culture, international and inter-civilizational relations, religion, labor and organization of public organizations are of great importance.¹³

Nuclear syntactic structures play an important role in production. The proponents of this model are that these structures are unique to different languages and are characterized by a common lexical structure and syntactic-logical relationship. The translational model of translation has also been criticized.

The communication model is viewed as a process of translation as a bilingual communication activity. It contains the sender and recipient, the code, and the communication channel (written and oral, corresponding to the genre of speech).

In conclusion, by teaching students the translation process models and informing them in the learning process, not only linguistic education is provided, but also the opportunities for teaching instruction through translation science are broader. This reflects the educational value of modern language teaching technologies.

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¹¹ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *Journal/NX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

¹² Madumarov Talatbek Tolibjonovich, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2021). PREREQUISITES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEASING MECHANISM IN PUBLIC - PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(SP), 5. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7MXR3>

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